

An Alternate Proof of the Stars and Bars Theorem

Amogh A. Jha

March 2025

Abstract

The stars and bars theorem is a classic theorem in combinatorics related to the distribution of indistinguishable objects among distinguishable containers. In this manuscript, we present an alternate proof of the same, approaching the problem via recursion and induction.

1 Introduction

Let $N(n, k)$ be the number of ways of distributing n indistinguishable objects among k distinguishable containers. The "Stars and Bars" Theorem states that

$$N(n, k) = \binom{n + k - 1}{k - 1}.$$

Since the objects are indistinguishable and the containers are distinguishable, a distribution is determined by the number of objects in each container. A container may contain no objects but the total number of objects distributed among the containers must be n , that is, all the objects must be distributed into containers.

2 Preliminary Lemmas

Lemma 1.

$$N(n, 2) = \sum_{i=0}^n 1.$$

Proof. With only two containers, the number of objects in the first container (say i) uniquely determines the number of objects in the second (that is, $n - i$). The first container may contain $0, 1, \dots, n$ objects—and in each case, there is only one possible distribution. Hence, the total number of distributions is just the number of cases— $n + 1$, which is the same as $\sum_{i=0}^n 1$.

$$N(n, 2) = \sum_{i=0}^n 1.$$

As an example, all the possible distributions of 5 objects among containers A and B are tabulated below.

Sl. No.	A	B
1	0	5
2	1	4
3	2	3
4	3	2
5	4	1
6	5	0

Lemma 2.

$$N(n, k + 1) = \sum_{i=0}^n N(i, k).$$

Proof. Consider the distribution of objects with respect to a particular container. The said container may contain $0, 1, \dots, n$ objects. In each case, if the container contains i objects, counting the number of distributions reduces to distributing $n - i$ objects among $k - 1$ containers.

Hence, to find the total number of distributions, we just sum over all cases to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} N(n, k + 1) &= \sum_{i=0}^n N(n - i, k) \\ &= N(n, k) + N(n - 1, k) + \dots + N(0, k) \\ &= N(0, k) + N(1, k) + \dots + N(n, k) \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n N(i, k) \end{aligned}$$

3 Finding a Closed-Form Expression

The two lemmas essentially enable us to compute N for any value of k . If we have a function for $k = 2$, we could use *Lemma 2* to compute a function for $n = 3$, and then for $n = 4$, etc.

For example, from *Lemma 2*,

$$N(n, 3) = \sum_{i=0}^n N(i, 2)$$

From *Lemma 1*,

$$N(n, 3) = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^i 1$$

Similarly,

$$N(n, 4) = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j 1$$

$$N(n, 5) = \sum_{i=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^i \sum_{k=0}^j \sum_{l=0}^k 1$$

The pattern here seems clear. We could conjecture a general form and use induction to establish the generality of the same.

Writing multiple summations is cumbersome. To abbreviate the algebra, let us introduce some notation. Let

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^k f \equiv \sum_{x_1=0}^n \sum_{x_2=0}^{x_1} \dots \sum_{x_k=0}^{x_{k-1}} f$$

where $x_1 = i$. Essentially, we are expressing k summations with one symbol. The iterating variable of a summation is the upper limit of next.

Observing the expressions for $k = 2$ through $k = 5$, we may conjecture that

$$N(n, k) = \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k-1} 1.$$

We will establish this result via induction. Let us state our induction hypothesis.

$$P(k) : N(n, k) = \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k-1} 1$$

From *Lemma 1*,

$$N(n, 2) = \sum_{i=0}^n 1 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{2-1} 1.$$

Hence, we have our base case verified. Consider $N(n, k + 1)$. From *Lemma 2*,

$$N(n, k + 1) = \sum_{i=0}^n N(i, k)$$

Assuming our induction hypothesis,

$$N(n, k + 1) = \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\sum_{j=0}^i\right)^{k-1} 1 = \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^k 1.$$

But this is $P(k + 1)$ and our proof by induction is complete.

We are essentially done with what we wanted to accomplish—an expression for $N(n, k)$. But is it equivalent to the standard result? In the rest of the manuscript, we simplify the multiple summations into binomial coefficients.

4 Manipulating the Expression

Lemma 3.

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^k 1 = \binom{n+k}{k}$$

Proof. We will prove this lemma via induction. Let us state our induction hypothesis.

$$P(k) : \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^k 1 = \binom{n+k}{k}.$$

Consider $k = 1$.

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^1 1 = n + 1 = \binom{n+1}{1}.$$

Hence, our base case is verified. Consider $\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k+1} 1$.

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k+1} 1 = \sum_{i=0}^n \left(\sum_{j=0}^i\right)^k 1$$

Assuming our induction hypothesis,

$$\left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k+1} 1 = \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{i+k}{k}$$

We could use the recurrence relation of binomial coefficients

$$\binom{n}{r} = \binom{n-1}{r-1} + \binom{n-1}{r}.$$

Replacing $n \rightarrow n + 1$ and $r \rightarrow r + 1$, and rearranging the terms, we get

$$\binom{n}{r} = \binom{n+1}{r+1} - \binom{n}{r+1}.$$

Using this result, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\sum_{i=0}^n\right)^{k+1} 1 &= \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{i+k}{k} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n \left\{ \binom{i+k+1}{k+1} - \binom{i+k}{k+1} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

Which is a neat telescopic sum.

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=0}^n \left\{ \binom{i+k+1}{k+1} - \binom{i+k}{k+1} \right\} &= \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{i+k+1}{k+1} - \sum_{i=0}^n \binom{i+k}{k+1} \\
&= \sum_{i=k+1}^{n+k+1} \binom{i}{k+1} - \sum_{i=k}^{n+k} \binom{i}{k+1} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=k+1}^{n+k} \binom{i}{k+1} + \binom{n+k+1}{k+1} \right) - \left(\binom{k}{k+1} + \sum_{i=k+1}^{n+k} \binom{i}{k+1} \right) \\
&= \binom{n+k+1}{k+1} - \binom{k}{k+1} \\
&= \binom{n+k+1}{k+1} - 0
\end{aligned}$$

But this is $P(k+1)$ and our proof by induction is complete.

5 Conclusion

From *Lemma 3*, the closed-form expression we found could be expressed as

$$N(n, k) = \binom{n+k-1}{k-1},$$

which is the standard statement of the Stars and Bars Theorem. Thus, we have supplied an alternate proof to the said theorem.